

SCIENTIFIC INTERPRETATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION FROM A THEORETICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract. *The article considers inclusive education in the 21st century as an approach to education based on concepts and values adequate to the challenges of the 4th industrial revolution, as well as an open system in terms of meeting the needs of children with limited health opportunities, and most importantly, as an effective means of avoiding discrimination and isolation. By reviewing its history, attention is drawn to the lack of uniformity in the attitude towards it in different periods of society's development, the diversity manifested in stages, and the arguments that condition it are presented. It is emphasized that since education is the most fundamental human right, inclusive education is important and, in itself, leads to the realization of another basic human right - the right to work and employment.*

The research provides a theoretical and technological interpretation of the concept of "Inclusive Education" as a national concept that is essentially consistent with traditions of tolerance with deep historical roots and an approach in the context of human rights.

Keywords: *system, structure, subsystem, integration, education system, inclusive education, educational needs, normalization model, social model, methodology.*

Relevance of the research topic. It is undeniable that civilization is developing in stages, corresponding to industrial revolutions. This process can exist in dialectical dependence on education based on scientific foundations, which is understood as the sharing (transmission from generation to generation) of human experience. The aforementioned eternal dialectic makes it necessary to identify constantly updated views on the theoretical and technological foundations of an open system and its implementation in terms of meeting the needs of children with disabilities, and brings the study of problems directly and indirectly related to education, as well as the cognitive issues that determine the solution of problems, among the requirements of scientific activity. It is undeniable that the quality of the organization and management of modern education - a system open to all learners and the implementation process - in terms of meeting the needs of children with disabilities, along with many arguments, depends on the level of understanding by its subject and familiarity with its important features. Therefore, we claim the relevance of the topic "Interpretation of inclusive education from a theoretical and technological aspect on scientific grounds".

The purpose of the study is to provide a scientific interpretation of the concept of "Inclusive Education" from a theoretical and **technological perspective**.

Methodological basis of the study. In the process of conducting the study, the "System-structural approach", which has been formed as an important branch of dialectics and has risen to the level of its alternative, based on L. Bertalanfi's "Idea of System Analysis" [9; 8] (the idea, the meaning of which is explained as an attempt to study the properties of an object based on the properties of its parts), empirical, empirical-theoretical and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, internal relations of forms of scientific cognition, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations were used as a methodological basis.

Interpretation of generalizations from research materials. There are many people who are discriminated against and excluded from education due to their health conditions, learning disabilities, race and social origin, religion, nationality, etc. Unfortunately, this discrimination

prevents every child from receiving an equal opportunity to receive an education and participate in social and cultural activities. However, there is an approach aimed at preventing this situation and creating equal opportunities for every child. This is called “inclusive education”. Inclusion is a process that ensures the adaptation of all citizens, primarily people with disabilities (PWDs), to society, and their transformation into equal individuals of society, like other people. Inclusive education is based on an ideology that takes the following directions as its basis: a) ensuring equal treatment for all people and avoiding any kind of discrimination; b) creating conditions in general education institutions for children with special educational needs. [10; 51]

When we look at the history of inclusive education for children with special needs, it becomes clear that the attitude of society towards them has not been the same at different periods of development. For example, if at one stage (the 12th century AD) society treated them with compassion, then a few centuries later this approach was replaced by a step towards emphasizing the learning abilities of children with special needs. Later, in the 70s-80s of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, society realized the need to teach children with special needs, along with their learning skills. The period from the beginning of the last century to the 60s of that century was characterized by the creation of special educational institutions for children with special needs, the provision of uninterrupted medical services and treatment. At this time, social and developmental adaptation factors were somewhat relegated to the background. The next stage, covering the 1960s-1980s, is known as the “normalization model”. This process is called “integration”. The model in question was first applied and developed in Scandinavia in 1970, and later in the USA and Canada.

The essence of the “normalization model” is determined by the following factors: children in need of special care should live in an environment close to a high level of normal life; the most favorable conditions for children in need of special care are their own homes; efforts should be made by the authorities to educate children in need of special care at home; regardless of the degree of the disease, conditions should be created for children in need of special care to receive education.

The last - the third stage covers the period from the 80s of the last century to the present and is called the “Social model”. The “Social model” implies that all children, regardless of their health, family status, abilities, religion, race, have equal rights in the educational process and in life. Observations show that since the 90s of the XIX century, the purpose and essence of inclusive education have changed significantly. That is, it is directed towards obtaining professional experience. Inclusive education in the 21st century is an approach to education based on concepts and values that are adequate to the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. This education is an open system in terms of meeting the needs of all children. Most importantly, inclusive education is an effective tool for avoiding discrimination and exclusion.

Inclusive education always combines high-quality, accessible education for all, which embodies excellence and equality. Inclusive education is a key pillar for the formation of a multicultural society in our globalized world. Inclusive education for the formation of a multicultural society is not limited to protecting the rights of people with disabilities. Inclusive education also seeks to eliminate racial, ethnic, cultural and gender stereotypes and to solve or improve problems related to racism and prejudice. Multicultural values can be linked to three components to support inclusive education: 1) self-transformation; 2) transformation of schools and the education system; 3) education of society. [1; 47-48]

According to our subjective understanding, inclusive education is conditioned by the following arguments: 1. The value of a person is measured by his abilities and achievements; 2. Each person has the ability to feel and think; 3. Everyone has the right to communicate and should be listened to; 4. All people need each other; 5. Authentic education can only exist in the context of real relationships; 6. All people need the support and friendship of their peers; 7. Progress for all students depends on what they know; 8. Diversity strengthens all aspects of human life.

Professor J. Jafarov writes that the philosophy of education of the modern era is rooted in new paradigms and values. While preserving its classical values as an enlightening and developmental process, education has also acquired a number of new universal values, one of the most important of

which is equality of rights in education. Since new values are formed in parallel with the globalization process, countries that fall under this process integrate these values into the education system, which in turn contributes to the education of people on a wider scale. It is gratifying that inclusive education is very popular in Azerbaijan, which is rapidly integrating into the world education space. This is not without reason. Thus, although inclusive education gives the impression of an artificial “imported” foreign concept in terms of semantic structure, it is essentially a national concept that is consistent with the traditions of tolerance with deep historical roots. What is new is the approach to inclusive education in the context of human rights. [5; 5-6]

The right to education is constitutionally guaranteed in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which also creates the basis for organizing inclusive education in our country. Inclusive education is the process of developing general education. It implies that education is accessible to all in terms of meeting the needs of all children. This also ensures that children with special needs receive education.

Inclusive education is important first of all because education is the most fundamental human right. In addition, it in itself leads to the provision of another basic human right - the right to work and employment. That is, access to education and participation in educational life are necessary for an individual to gain an independent life. It also: a) increases students' self-confidence; b) develops communication skills. In addition, inclusion has the following important benefits: c) all children can be part of their community and develop a sense of belonging; d) it creates more effective opportunities for learning; students with different abilities are more motivated when they learn in the same classroom as other students; e) successful inclusion allows for the development of individual strengths and potential; e) it encourages parents to be involved in the school and to collaborate with teachers in the education of their children.

Inclusive education in our country is not limited to being just a scientific and pedagogical theory, and a number of measures have been implemented. In our country, the implementation of the "State Program for the Development of Inclusive Education for Persons with Disabilities in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2018-2024", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated December 14, 2017, aimed at involving children with disabilities in education together with other children (inclusive education), having a positive impact on their mental development and ensuring their integration into society by involving them in education together with healthy children. [4; 77-78] It is undeniable that the implementation of the aforementioned Program has had an impact on the development of inclusive education in subsequent periods.

As the world develops and new pedagogical trends emerge, the essence of education and the views on it change and are renewed. If we compare the education system that existed at the beginning of the 20th century with the current education system, we will see that not only the content and essence of education have been renewed, but the value system that education contains has also undergone changes. If we look at the educational trends of the modern era, we will observe that the most important call is “education is for everyone”. The “Education Law” of the Republic of Azerbaijan states that all people, regardless of language, religion, race, or nationality, have the right to education. It is worth emphasizing that in any case, all people are involved in education. However, there are, of course, some specializations in the very essence of this involvement. There are educational institutions for children in need of special care in Azerbaijan, and in these educational institutions, educational content appropriate for students with disabilities is applied. In general, we can say that the existence of special educational institutions is an advantage. When analyzing the educational programs and standards of regular educational institutions, it can be said that most of them will pose difficulties for children with disabilities. Regardless of whether it is a special educational institution or a general educational institution, the existence of educational institutions is an important value. The main goal here is to involve all children in education. Inclusive education is the need of the hour.

The fact that children receiving inclusive education study together with healthy children of their own age leads to their comprehensive development. These children try to repeat the achievements of their peers, seek the strength to act, speak, and act like them. Such children do not consider themselves

useless, they adapt to the team, and feel that they are needed. Teachers and parents should pay attention to the adaptation of such children to the team and society. Teachers should keep such students in mind during events and competitions. All this stimulates their comprehensive development. At the same time, carrying out certain work and implementing measures to improve the development of inclusive education will be beneficial for the education of children in need of special care. [3; 37]

The state strategy reflects the work to be done to improve the education of children with disabilities. These include: the preparation of development and inclusive training programs for children with special needs; the creation of an inclusive training methodology that ensures the integration of children with special needs into life and the educational environment; the application of optimal inclusive education models to provide opportunities for the education and social adaptation of children with special needs; the provision of targeted additional training on inclusive education for educators in preschool and general education institutions.

One of these important issues included in the state education strategy, the creation of a methodology for general education, attracts our attention the most, as we have been conducting pedagogical research directly and indirectly related to this issue for a long time.

The approach to events and processes, their understanding, with the so-called "system-structure" view, which has been formed as a branch of the dialectical method since the 1930s, is a characteristic feature of the modern era. [9;8] According to this approach, education is a broader system than the inclusive education system and should transform the inclusive education system into itself as a specific subsystem. The essence of the inclusive education system transformed in such a broad system should be determined by the nature of the elements of the system that contains it and their behavioral relationships, and the specificity of the relationship of the object with the conditions. Based on a logical basis, we can say that the education system is characterized not only by its structure and functions, but also by the nature of the unity of structure and function, the nature of this unity. At the same time, the continuous, important, and necessary interaction of elements also characterizes the nature of inclusive education, which exists as a subsystem. [6;105-106] In our opinion, the subsystems of the education system, divided into managers and those managed, should have such a special dialectical unity that they include both children with a wide range of abilities and those in need of special care as sides of the unit. In this system, children should not be divided into healthy and those in need of special care; when admitting children to general education classes, it is necessary to pay attention to their needs and, taking into account these needs, formulate specific goals for each of them. *Odur ki, inklüziv təhsil uşağın xüsusi ehtiyaclarının müəyyənləşdirilməsindən başlamalı, onun həyata keçirilməsi prosesinin məntiqi axarında idarəolunan altsistemin imkandayıcı elementlərindən biri olan uşağı sinif kollektivinin integrativ üzvünə çevirməlidir.*

It is the right of a child with disabilities to have their educational needs met in general education institutions with special facilities. The education system must be open to an inclusive approach. [7; 313] Creating equal conditions for learners is the principle of implementing education. In this process, the importance of meeting the educational needs of a child with disabilities and the humane nature of the process in question should be clear to education administrators, parents and society, and they should perform their functions sensitively. For this, along with a number of undesirable stereotypes, the shortcomings in both the theoretical and technological preparation of enabling persons, especially teachers and educators, who are included in the subsystem of administrators of the inclusive education system, should be eliminated. Whether the existence of misconceptions in society's views on inclusive education, the lack of a perfect cognitive approach of parents to their child's health limitations, or the inadequate level of training of specialists who should implement the pedagogical process, leads to a violation of the "whole-part" dialectic in the inclusive education system. Violation of the elements and subsystems in the system undermines its effectiveness, and a child with health limitations is not transformed into an integrated member of the class collective in general educational institutions where special conditions are created.

Inclusive education is a system of social nature and has a specific emergent nature. Its emergent nature is not simply related to the transfer of human experience to a controlled party based on some standards, but to the goal of meeting the educational needs of the child entering the system. Educational needs are not a concept that applies only to children with limited health opportunities. This applies to everyone with different levels of health opportunities. If we symbolize the most limited state of health opportunities with zero and the absence of limitations with one, the health opportunities of children will be located in the open interval (0;1). Here, the health opportunities of a child are not equal to the “zero” and “one” that we accept symbolically, but are between zero and one. The unity between the child's educational needs and his health opportunities and development potential is the main sign of the management of the educational process in which he is involved. The realization of the said unity, which has become a matter of understanding for every teacher and educator, is necessary because it is the right of every individual child to benefit from the time allocated for the implementation of education. The educational needs of the child are met depending on how he is involved in activities and communication. It is precisely in this oriented social activity that the child takes his opportunities to a new level of development, benefits from the point of view of satisfying his educational needs. In short, the “opportunity - action - new quality” model becomes operational.

In her book *Inclusion for the 21st Century*, Linda Graham explains that to create inclusive education, educators must be very aware of both the content of the curriculum and the diversity of learners. If they understand and comprehend both, this knowledge will enable them to overcome the difficulties in teaching, teaching methods and assessment. If educators think that the problem is always with the learner, if they understand that creating equal opportunities in education means teaching all students in the same way, giving them the same resources and conducting the same assessments, then they will not succeed in creating inclusion. One of the best ways to help learners is to remove barriers to learning. One approach that can help achieve this is Universal Design for Learning (UDL). This approach works by identifying learners' strengths and weaknesses and removing barriers to learning. [10; 52]

Universal Design for Learning is based on 3 principles: 1. Engagement (Why do we learn?); 2. Presentation (What do we learn?); and 3. Action (How do we learn?).

Scientific sources (see: [10; 49-50]) show that all three principles are based on the activity of the neurocognitive network of our brain. Involving students in the process in various ways activates the question “Why?” in our brain. Students ask themselves the questions “Why do I need to learn this?” or “When will I use this information?” By involving students in the learning process, it is possible to clarify this concern of theirs and establish a connection with the emotional-affective sphere. In other words, by creating interest in the lesson and involving students in the teaching, an emotional connection is created with the issues they will learn. In this case, it is advisable to involve students in individual and group work to motivate them, and it is useful to provide them with opportunities to engage in live or online discussions.

Presenting information in a variety of ways activates the “What?” question in our brains, which is related to the parts of our brains that understand and process content. Presenting information in a variety of forms—such as graphics and animations, text, and audio, highlighting key features of the content, and activating prior knowledge—helps students develop a deep and complete conceptual understanding of the topic. Providing students with rubrics, guidelines, and examples plays a critical role in their learning in the classroom.

Implementing activities in different ways activates the question “how?” in our minds. This principle is a strategic approach that allows us to adapt the information we have learned to a different and new context. It is a sensible working style to give students a wide range of options to present what they have learned in different ways and to support them with approaches and feedback that are appropriate to their level.

In order for each child to develop at his or her own level and not be left behind by anyone, differentiation must be applied in addition to inclusive education. Differentiation can be implemented

through content, process, learning environment, and materials used. This should be based on 3-4 different types of activities in reading, writing, grammar, phonetics, mathematical rules, assessment, and oral speech. For this, the teacher should conduct diagnostic interviews and be familiar with the children's thinking, perception, unique skills, psychology, and interests.

In particular, it should be emphasized that the formation of an inclusive culture in schools is extremely important for creating a supportive environment. In a school with an inclusive environment, the fact that everyone is different is accepted; factors that support learning exist and are used correctly; different learning experiences are applied to each student; there is an innovative and creative environment; there are principles of an individual approach; there is a safe environment for everyone; there is an environment that respects the participation of all members of the school community and values everyone; classes are designed to meet the needs of each student.

It should be noted that one of the characteristics that negatively affects the formation of a culture of inclusion in schools is the attitude towards students with disabilities. That is, sometimes in the classroom, expressions such as "sick child", "defective child", etc. are used in relation to students with disabilities or some social or physical differences. Such an approach leads to a decrease in students' self-confidence, their poor involvement in the learning process, low academic achievement, and most importantly, their emotional damage. In general, it is unacceptable to address students with stigmatizing words, regardless of their shortcomings or differences. [11]

Inclusive education limits and minimizes the opportunities for children with disabilities to form groups, exclude them from those groups, display angry behavior, and express hurtful thoughts. Even if it is minimized, there are bullies in society, especially in schools, who are always waiting for an opportunity to initiate bullying. So what should we do? Should we draw a large, imaginary, forbidden barrier between the bully and the bullied? Of course, this seemingly absurd solution can only set us back a few years. While we have come such a long way through inclusive education, we should not ignore the gaps. Therefore, it is necessary to get to the heart of the matter. It is very important to look at Buller's life path. It is clear that school is of particular importance in the upbringing of children. However, if the parents do not first instill the polishing work in their children at home, no matter how hard the school tries, the principle of completeness will be violated. The parent must raise his child in such a way that he knows how to deal with people with disabilities in public life, as well as at school. [12]

By the way, let us also note that a child with a disability experiences fundamental psychological changes such as withdrawal, avoiding other children, and not getting close to them. The child's attitude towards family members and himself also changes. As a result, such children develop irritability and mental disorders. Most bullying incidents usually occur when there are no adults around. Because bullies feel free and uninhibited. Violence can occur on the road, in the hallway, in school cafeterias, changing rooms, school toilets, and gyms while walking to school, so it is useful to be careful in this regard. [13; 52-78]

It is no secret that the family is the place where the first and main role is played in the development, formation and socialization of the personality, where it receives the first value. The role of the attitude and behavior of parents towards their child in the self-evaluation of the child as a person cannot be denied. For many years, a "tradition" has been formed in the family to hide children with limited health opportunities (even those with the slightest physical disability) from society when they are born. The inappropriateness of the attitude towards children with limited health opportunities at different times has conditioned the existence of such a "tradition". It is natural that these complexes that exist in parents are also transmitted to children. As a result, a certain complex arises in children with limited health opportunities against society, and a negative tendency to withdraw into themselves is formed in them. [2; 81]

In fairness, it should be said that today, various activities are being carried out to ensure that everyone, without discrimination, actively participates in all spheres of society as equal members. Inclusive education is one of these areas. This creates a sense of satisfaction in every member of society.

Scientific novelty of the research. 1. Inclusive education in the 21st century is defined as: a) an approach to education based on concepts and values adequate to the challenges of the 4th industrial revolution; b) an open system in terms of meeting the needs of children with limited health opportunities; c) an effective means of avoiding discrimination and exclusion. 2. Since education is the most fundamental human right, inclusive education is a value and in itself leads to the provision of another basic right - the right to work and employment.

Practical significance of the research. In terms of meeting the needs of children with disabilities, understanding and familiarity with the important features of modern education - a system open to all learners - by the subject of its organization and management has a positive impact on preventing errors in the real pedagogical process.

The result. 1) The civilizational process, which is developing gradually in accordance with the industrial revolutions, exists in dialectical dependence on education, which is understood as the sharing of human experience (transmission from generation to generation); 2) The aforementioned eternal dialectic makes it necessary to identify constantly updated views on the theoretical and technological foundations of an open system and its implementation in terms of meeting the needs of children with disabilities, and brings the study of problems directly and indirectly related to education, as well as cognitive issues that condition the solution of problems, among the requirements of scientific activity; 3) In terms of meeting the needs of children with disabilities, the quality of the organization and management of modern education - a system open to all learners - and its implementation process depends, along with many arguments, on the level of understanding by its subject and his or her awareness of its important features.

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